

Rapid Cavity Volume Calculation of Marine Propeller Using Lift Equivalent Method

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Abstract. Cavitation on the propeller blade produces pressure fluctuations on the ship stern, which is one of the causes of ship vibration. It has been established that the amplitude of pressure fluctuations induced by unsteady cavitation is proportional to the second time derivative of the cavity volume. Therefore, accurate prediction of the cavity volume variation is very important. The authors have developed a practical method based on an original simple surface panel method “SQCM” to calculate the cavity volume of sheet cavitation, tip vortex cavitation, and tip supercavitation. For sheet cavitation, the cavity shape is accurately determined using the free streamline theory. Although the calculation time is much shorter than that of CFD, it is not sufficiently short compared to the expected calculation time based on potential flow. In order to improve practicality, this paper introduces a new approach that calculates the sheet cavity area, which requires the most computation time, using the lift equivalent method and applying the free streamline theory only to the cavity thickness. This new method considerably reduces computation time by eliminating the need for iterative adjustment of the cavity length at each blade section of the propeller. Furthermore, despite the shorter computation time, the estimation accuracy remains comparable to that of the previous method, which rigorously calculates the cavity length. The calculated cavitation pattern, cavity volume, and pressure fluctuation are compared with experiments and previous method. The present method reproduces pressure fluctuation amplitudes, including higher-order components, with comparable accuracy but requires only one-fourth the computation time.

Keywords: *SQCM, Propeller Cavitation, Lift Equivalent Method, Cavity Volume, Pressure Fluctuation*

1 Introduction

Unsteady cavitation due to ship wake generates significant pressure fluctuation on ship stern, which causes hull vibration and structural damage. Therefore, it is very important to predict the pressure fluctuation induced by a cavitating propeller at the propeller design stage.

Calculation methods for propeller cavitation and pressure fluctuations induced by cavitation have previously been presented [1]. These methods are based on a simple surface panel method, “SQCM,” developed at Kyushu University [2]. A key feature of this cavitation modeling is that the cross flow component around the blade tip is taken into account in the free streamline theory, which determines the sheet cavity shape. A tip cavitation model was also incorporated into the calculation method [3]. This model consists of a tip vortex cavitation model and a local undeveloped supercavitation model. Furthermore, a practical prediction method for cavitation on a single key blade was developed by precomputing the inflow velocity components to account for the interaction between blades [4]. This approach reduces the calculation time by decreasing the size of the solution matrix. The calculation method described above is both practical and accurate. However, in the propeller design stage, quick predictions are sometimes required, and more rapid calculation methods are needed.

The reason for the long calculation time is that the method follows theoretical formulations to ensure simulation accuracy. Nonlinear analysis using streamline theory requires many iterative calculations to obtain a converged cavity shape. However, nonlinear theory is indispensable for the prediction of pressure fluctuations to calculate the cavity volume variation.

In this study, the previous method is improved by introducing a more practical approach using the lift equivalent method [5]. The lift equivalent method is a classical and empirical approach, but it is still widely used today as a highly effective method of predicting cavitation occurrence areas. In the sheet cavitation calculation based on free streamline theory, the most time-consuming process is the iterative calculations required to determine the cavity length at each radial blade section. In the proposed method, the cavity length at each blade section is

precomputed using the lift equivalent method and used as a known value in the cavitation calculation. This approach eliminates the need for iterative calculations to adjust the cavity length to the appropriate value, and as a result, the computation time can be significantly reduced.

The calculated results of cavity volume, cavitation patterns, and fluctuating pressure are shown for two types of propellers. These results are also compared with experimental data and results obtained using by the previous method to validate the proposed method.

2 Calculation method

SQCM (Source and QCM) uses source distributions [6] on the propeller blade surface and discrete vortex distributions arranged on the mean camber surface according to QCM (Quasi-Continuous vortex lattice Method) [7], which is well known as one of the lifting surface methods. The formulation of SQCM is described in the paper [2]. SQCM was applied to the calculation of unsteady propeller cavitation and pressure fluctuation induced by cavitation, including tip vortex cavitation and tip supercavitation [3] and [4]. This chapter explains the outline of the calculation method related to the proposed approach and the improvements from the previous calculation method.

2.1 Calculation method for sheet cavitation

It is assumed that the pressure on the cavity surface is constant, according to the free streamline theory. The difficulty in the analysis of the cavitating flow is that not only the zero normal velocity condition but also the constant pressure condition must be satisfied on the cavity surface. On the other hand, the blade surface that is not covered by the cavity must satisfy the zero normal velocity condition. In this section, the treatment of the cavity surface is described.

Cavitation number σ_n is defined by

$$\sigma_n = \frac{p_0 - p_v}{\frac{1}{2} \rho n^2 D^2} \quad (1)$$

Where p_0 , p_v , ρ , n , and D are the static pressure in the undisturbed inflow, the saturated vapor pressure, the density of the fluid, the revolutions per second and the propeller diameter. And the tangential velocity on the cavity surface is given by the following equation:

$$V_T = \sqrt{|\vec{V}_I|^2 + \sigma_n n^2 D^2 - 2 \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t}} \quad (2)$$

Where \vec{V}_I , Φ , and t are the inflow velocity vector, the perturbation potential on the cavity surface and time.

First of all, the initial cavity length ℓ_μ is assumed for each blade section, and the cavitation number σ_n is specified to obtain the tangential velocity V_T . The source and vortex distributions are determined from the following equation:

$$\frac{\Phi_{\mu v} - \Phi_{\mu v-1}}{\Delta S_{\mu v}} = V_T' \quad (3)$$

$$V_T' = \sqrt{V_T^2 - V_{Cr}^2} \quad (4)$$

Where $\Phi_{\mu v}$ and $\Phi_{\mu v-1}$ are the total velocity potential at the control point of the v -th and $(v-1)$ -th cavity surface panels at μ -th blade section. $\Delta S_{\mu v}$ denotes the distance between these two control points (Figure 1). V_T' means the modified tangential velocity obtained by considering the cross flow component V_{Cr} . Although the boundary condition (Eq.(3)) is based on two-

Figure 1. Model of cavitating section.

dimensional flow at the wing section, the tangential velocity V_T is satisfied under three-dimensional flow by subtracting V_{Cr} in advance.

When calculating the velocity on the cavity surface using the boundary condition, the velocity vector does not satisfy the zero normal velocity condition on the cavity surface. Therefore, the source panels must be arranged to align with the flow direction using the following equation:

$$V_T \frac{\partial h}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \vec{V} \cdot \vec{n} \quad (5)$$

Where s denotes the distance from the cavity detachment point along the cavity surface, and h denotes the cavity thickness. \vec{V} and \vec{n} are the calculated velocity vector and the unit normal vector on the cavity surface. By iterating the calculations of Eqs. (3) and (5), the free streamline that simultaneously satisfies both boundary conditions can be obtained.

After the cavity shape converges, the openness at cavity trailing edge $\delta_{E\mu}$ (Figure 1), is compared with the target value $\delta_{ET\mu}$, and the cavity length ℓ_μ is adjusted using the following equation:

$$\ell_\mu^{(j+1)} = \ell_\mu^{(j)} + w(\delta_{ET\mu} - \delta_{E\mu}) \quad (6)$$

Where j and w denote the iteration number for adjusting the cavity length and a suitable weighting coefficient, respectively. After the cavity length converges at all blade sections, the cavity volume at the current time step is calculated, and the calculation proceeds to the next step.

Figure 2 shows a flowchart for the calculation of sheet cavitation at a certain time step. There are two loops in this calculation. One is for cavity shape convergence (II-III-A-II), and the other is for adjusting the cavity length (I-II-III-A-B-I), which includes the former. Regarding branch A, a few iterations are sufficient to converge the cavity shape. However, a considerable number of iterations are required at branch B. From Figure 2, it can be seen that if the cavity length is assigned as a known value, the calculation time can be significantly reduced.

Figure 2. Flowchart for sheet cavitation calculation.

2.2 Cavity length estimation using the lift equivalent method

An attempt is made to eliminate loop “I-II-III-A-B- I” using the lift equivalent method. It is empirically known that, when cavitation occurs, as long as the cavity area is not very large and the load is not high, it does not cause a significant change in thrust. The method of calculating the cavity length using the assumption that the lifts are equal is called the lift equivalent method [5]. Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of a typical pressure distribution on a blade surface. As shown in the figure, the area where the pressure is lower than the cavitation number ($-$) is equal to the area where it is higher than the cavitation number ($+$), and the cavity length is calculated based on this balance.

Before performing the cavitation calculation, the proposed method calculates the unsteady propeller flow without cavitation and simultaneously determines the cavity length at each blade section and time step.

In the cavitation calculation, the cavity lengths stored in a data file are provided, and only the cavity thickness is calculated based on the free streamline theory. In this case, the openness at the cavity trailing edge may deviate slightly from the appropriate value, but the present calculation method prioritizes computation time by eliminating loop “I-II-III-A-B- I”. In the previous method, it is necessary to perform cavitation calculations even in cases without cavitation. In the present method, the range of blade

Figure 3. Concept of lift equivalent method.

angles at which cavitation occurs is already known, which also contributes to reducing the computation time. This lift-equivalent procedure is applied independently to each blade section, assuming that the blade surface flow is circumferential. Consequently, the method may lose accuracy near the blade tip, where three-dimensional effects are significant. An appropriate correction method for the tip region is left for future work.

In this study, the pressure fluctuation by the second time derivative of the spherical cavity volume [11] is applied as following equation:

$$\Delta p(t) = \frac{\alpha \rho}{4\pi \ell} \frac{d^2 V_C}{dt^2} \quad (7)$$

Where $\Delta p(t)$ is the half amplitude of fluctuating pressure, ℓ is the distance between the estimation point and the center of the cavity, V_C is the cavity volume. This theory generally overestimates $\Delta p(t)$ because it does not take into account the void fraction and the fact that the real bubbles are not spherical. α is the correction coefficient to attenuate overestimation. The coefficient of the pressure fluctuation ΔK_p is defined as following equation:

$$\Delta K_p = \frac{\Delta p(t)}{\rho n^2 D^2} \quad (8)$$

ΔK_p can be expressed using Fourier series as following equation:

$$\Delta K_p = - \sum_{i=1} K_{piN} \cdot \cos(iN(\theta - \varphi_{iN})) \quad (9)$$

Where K_{piN} and φ_{iN} are the amplitude and phase of i -th order frequency component. N is the number of blades.

3 Validation

3.1 Experiment

In this study, two types of propellers, the Seiun-Maru-I highly skewed propeller (HSP-II) and a coasting vessel propeller (M.P.700 [8]), are taken for the validation of the present method. Table 1 shows the principal particulars and Figure 4 and 5 show the model propellers for the experiment and the panel arrangements for the cavitation calculation. The experiments were conducted in Large Cavitation Tunnel in National Maritime Research Institute [9] and [10]. Figure 6 shows the wake distributions on the propeller plane by wire mesh screen regarding Seiun-Maru-I HSP-II and M.P.700. Figure 7 and 8 show the test section and the location of pressure transducer of the flat plate.

Table 1. Principal particulars of propellers.

	Seiun-Maru-I HSP-II	M.P.No.700
Diameter D_p [m]	0.250	0.240
Pitch ratio at 0.7R	0.9940	0.6059
Expanded area ratio	0.7000	0.4791
Boss ratio	0.1972	0.1750
Number of blade Z	5	4
Skew angle [deg]	45.0	25.0
Rake angle [deg]	-3.03	4.13
Blade section	Modified SRI-B	NACA
Direction of rotation	Right	Right

Figure 4. Model propellers.

Figure 5. Panel arrangements for cavitation model.

Figure 6. Axial wake distributions.

Figure 7. Test section of cavitation tunnel.

Figure 8. Location of pressure transducer of the flat plate.

3.2 Seiun-Maru-I HSP-II

Figure 9 shows the cavitation patterns without cavity thickness, calculated by the lift equivalent method, and with cavity thickness by free streamline theory. Both have the same cavity length. The latter appears larger because the cavity surface is three-dimensional.

Figure 9. Cavitation patterns of Seiun-Maru-I HSP-II ($K_T=0.201$, $\sigma_n=2.99$).
Upper: Lift equivalent method (w/o cavity thickness), Lower: w/ cavity thickness.

Figure 10 compares the cavitation patterns between the experiment and the calculated results. The calculated results include those obtained by the previous method, which precisely adjusts the openness at the cavity trailing edge, and those by the present method. Although the phase of cavity development and collapse is slightly different from that observed in the experiment, the cavitation phenomena are well reproduced by the calculation. When comparing the calculated results, those obtained by the present method are slightly advanced in phase but still adequately capture the phenomenon. One possible explanation for the phase offset between the computational

results is that the cavity length estimate obtained using the lift-equivalent method does not account for cavitation-induced changes in the flow field. This issue requires further investigation in our future works.

Figure 11 shows the cavity shapes calculated using both the previous method and the present method. As mentioned earlier, the phase advance in the present method occurs earlier than that in the previous method. However, there is no significant difference in the maximum cavity thickness.

Figures 12 and 13 compare the cavity area and cavity volume between the experimental and calculated results. The calculated values for both cavity area and volume are larger than the experimental results, but the cause of this discrepancy is currently under investigation. When comparing the calculated values, a phase shift is observed, however, they coincide during the process of cavity volume development. This is a favorable result because cavity volume is more important than cavity area for calculating the fluctuating pressure.

Figure 10. Cavitation patterns of Seiun-Maru-I HSP-II ($K_T=0.201$, $\sigma_n=2.99$), Upper: experiment, Lower: calculations by previous method (left) and present method (right).

Figure 11. Comparisons of cavity shapes of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II ($K_T=0.201$, $\sigma_n=2.99$).

Figure 12. Cavity area of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II.

Figure 13. Cavity volume of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II.

Figure 14 shows the fluctuating pressure induced by the cavitating propeller during one revolution at P3 (Figure 8). The left figure shows the results obtained by the previous method, and the right figure shows those obtained by the present method. These are compared with the experimental results. To facilitate waveform comparison, the phases of the calculated results are aligned with those of the experimental results. Although the previous method, which involves more accurate calculations, is closer to the experimental results, the present method achieves sufficiently realistic fluctuating pressure with a much shorter computation time.

Figure 15 shows the amplitude of pressure fluctuation at P3. The calculated amplitudes reproduces the experimental data not only for the first-order frequency component but also for the second-order component. Moreover, the present calculation method reproduces the experimental data with the same level of accuracy as the previous method.

Figure 14. Fluctuating pressure in one revolution at P3 of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II, Left: Previous method, Right: Present method ($K_T=0.201$, $\sigma_n=2.99$).

Figure 15. Amplitude of pressure fluctuation at P3 of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II ($K_T=0.201$, $\sigma_n=2.99$).

Furthermore, the computation time required by the present method is approximately one-fourth that of the previous method, and its practicality in predicting pressure fluctuation induced by a cavitating propeller has been significantly improved.

3.3 Coasting vessel propeller M.P.700

Figure 16 compares the cavitation patterns between the experimental results and the calculated results. The calculated results includes those obtained by the previous method and those obtained by the present method. As in the case of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II, the results obtained by the present method are slightly advanced in phase compared to the previous method. Although this tendency is more pronounced than in the case of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II, it can be said that the experimental phenomenon is successfully reproduced by the present method.

Figure 17 shows the amplitude of pressure fluctuation at P3. Compared to the case of Seiu-Maru-I HSP-II, the difference between the results obtained by the previous method and those obtained by the present method is larger, except for the first-order component. However, the accuracy of the present method is maintained at the same level as that of the previous method. The reason why the difference between the results of these calculation methods varies depending on the type of propeller will be investigated in our future work.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents a very rapid and practical calculation method for cavity volume, which is important for predicting pressure fluctuation induced by a cavitating propeller. The present method uses the free streamline theory to calculate sheet cavitation, as in the previous method, but introduces the lift equivalent method instead of iterative calculations to determine the cavity length at each blade section. Two types of propellers were calculated in this paper. Although the phase of cavity generation is shifted in the present method compared to the previous method, it has been confirmed that the variation in cavity volume can be represented in almost the same way. As a result, the present method reproduces the experimental results for the amplitudes of fluctuating pressure, including higher order frequency components, with the same level of accuracy as the previous method.

The computation time is approximately one-fourth that of the previous method. Therefore, the present method is innovative from the viewpoint of practicality. We plan to apply the proposed method to many types of propellers and validate it to provide a practical tool for early-stage propeller design in the near future.

Figure 16. Cavitation patterns of M.P.700 ($K_T=0.124$, $\sigma_n=1.37$).
Upper: experiment, Lower: calculations by previous method (left) and present method (right).

Figure 17. Amplitude of pressure fluctuation at P3 of M.P.700 ($K_T=0.124$, $\sigma_n=1.37$).

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